

NON ISOTHERMAL REACTIVE FLOW MODELLING IN PULTRUSION PROCESS LOOKING TOWARD VOIDS PREDICTION

Pierpaolo Carlone¹, Nicola Pasquino² and Gaetano S. Palazzo³

¹Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Salerno
Via Giovanni Paolo II, 84084, Fisciano, Italy
Email: pcarlone@unisa.it web page: <http://www.unisa.it>

²Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Salerno
Via Giovanni Paolo II, 84084, Fisciano, Italy
Email: nipasquino@unisa.it web page: <http://www.unisa.it>

³Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Salerno
Via Giovanni Paolo II, 84084, Fisciano, Italy
Email: gspalazzo@unisa.it web page: <http://www.unisa.it>

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ABSTRACT

The present work presents a procedure aiming at void prediction, based on the coupling between an impregnation model, a thermo-chemical model and a stress/strain model, in a conventional pultrusion process. The impregnation model describes the resin flow and pressure distribution in the initial portion of the die, typically characterized by a convergent cross section. The model is based on the solution of a non-homogeneous non-isothermal/reactive multiphase model, using a finite volume scheme. The thermochemical model describes the heat transfer and degree of cure evolution of the processing resin in the die, as well as in the post die region. Finally, the stress/strain model computes the part distortion and in process stresses due to thermal, chemical, mechanical strains. An applicative case study is presented, simulating the impregnation step of the pultrusion process of a fiberglass-epoxy resin composite rod.

1 INTRODUCTION

Pultrusion is a highly automated process suitable to manufacture rectilinear polymeric composites profiles characterized by constant cross section [1]. During the last two decades, pultrusion process has experienced a continuous growing within the composites industry, due to its cost-effectiveness and high product quality. A positive trend is expected also in the near future, due to the lower energy intensity, i.e. the amount of energy needed to obtain one unit mass of product, exhibited by pultrusion process if compared to all other composites manufacturing processes [2]. This intriguing feature makes pultruded products highly competitive with respect to metallic materials.

In concept, the process is quite simple: reinforcement fibers are collimated by some guiders and impregnated by the resin in an open bath or employing a resin injection chamber. Impregnated fibers are then pulled through the forming and curing die. Within the die, the material changes its status from reactive liquid to gel and then vitrified solid. At the end of the process, the cured and solidified product is pulled using reciprocating or caterpillar mechanical systems and then cut into the desired length, ranging from less than one meter up to several kilometers for special applications.

Despite this simple appearance, the analysis of process dynamics and the definition of the optimal processing parameters is a challenging task, due to the mutual interactions between involved physical phenomena, related to resin flow and reinforcement impregnation, heat transfer, species conversion, phase changes and stress-strain development [3], as schematized in Figure 1. In this framework, actual contributes achievable by means of process modelling and simulations are well evidenced in [4-13]. In literature, several interesting investigations can be found aiming at process development, mainly focusing on the prediction of temperature and degree of cure, however, limited effort has been spent so

far to predict voids content and distribution into the final product. The relevance of this aspect is well highlighted in previous reports discussing the drastic reduction of mechanical properties observed increasing the porosity fraction [14]. Early models generally neglected the mutual interaction between involved phenomena, on the base of some simplifying assumptions.

Figure 1: Die and post-die regions in pultrusion highlighting involved phenomena

In this paper, a numerical approach aiming at the integration between the simulations of different physics involved in pultrusion is discussed. The target of the ongoing research is the development of a computational tool assisting process planning and optimization. Final degree of cure, temperature peak and thermal gradients, residual stresses and induced distortion and void content and distribution are considered as main objectives of the process design. The procedure is based on the coupling of three different models, simulating i. fluid flow during the impregnation stage, ii. heat transfer and resin reaction in the die as well as post-die region and finally iii. stress-strain development in the same domain. Fundamentals of the thermochemical as well as stress-strain calculations are briefly recalled within this paper, being these aspects widely analyzed elsewhere. The impregnation process, representing the main contribution of this work, is discussed in more details. The process is simulated by means of a CFD multiphase non-isothermal reactive model, evaluating the pressure and velocity fields at the die inlet. The impregnation process of a unidirectional carbon glass/epoxy resin cylindrical rod is herein discussed.

2 PULTRUSION PROCESS MODELLING

In literature several theoretical models have been proposed to predict the void growth and dissolution during the manufacturing process of polymeric composite materials [15-17]. Despite the solved governing equations, cited reports converge on the basic information needed to particularize each void model. An exhaustive and correct knowledge of the liquid pressure (taking into account the pressure increase induced by the tapered or rounded die inlet), temperature field, material properties (liquid viscosity and solid mechanical properties), and internal stresses was indicated as imperative. The aforementioned properties, however, are not deducible solving a model focused on one physical or chemical phenomenon (heat transfer, resin reaction, resin flow, etc.), due to mutual interactions between involved physics. In more details, liquid pressure increase is strongly influenced by the resin viscosity [3, 9,10,18], which, in turn depends on local temperature and degree of cure [3,4,19]. Similar considerations apply also to resin (hence processing composite) mechanical properties after gelation [8,11,18,19]. Temperature field and cure reaction are intimately related [3-8,11-13,18,19]. Indeed (thermosetting) resin conversion is typically an exothermic process, therefore it is characterized by some heat generation; while reaction activation, rate, and mode (kinetic or diffusive) are temperature

and degree of cure dependent. Finally, all aforementioned characteristics rely on some process parameters, such as heating profile and pulling speed, as clearly demonstrated in the herein cited bibliography. These considerations lead to the coupling of multi-physical aspects as schematized in Figure 2. It should be noted that some couplings are not considered in the proposed approach since no evident proof of their relevance is available in literature or, in some cases, negligible influence was proved [3]. In what follows, theoretical basis of each model are discussed.

Figure 2: Integrated computational approach in pultrusion looking towards void prediction

2.1 Impregnation Analysis.

In a conventional pultrusion process, reinforcing fibers are wetted out inside the resin bath before entering the heating die. After the impregnation, wetted fibers typically show an excess of resin with respect to the amount strictly needed in the final product. What is more, a certain amount of air is also entrapped in the resin, as can be seen in Figure 3. Impregnated fibers advance due the applied pulling force; however, their movement is somehow opposed by the viscous drag induced by the stationary catalyzed resin in the resin bath as well as by the collimation resistance exhibited by the dry fibers on the creel rack. As a consequence, before entering the die wetted fibers are pre-tensioned and proceed along an approximately straight path (Figure 3).

Die inlet is generally characterized by a tapered or rounded shape, in order to compact the material, reduce damage to the reinforcing fibers and increase the pressure of the liquid resin with respect to the atmospheric value [9,10,18]. The impregnation model describes the pressure distribution and the resin flow in the first part of the die, including the tapered or rounded zone and a portion of the straight die (Figure 3). The computational domain was divided into two different subdomain, namely the fluid and the porous sub-domains, whose main difference is related to the presence (or not) of the reinforcing fibers. In particular, in the fluid sub-domain, pressure and velocity field were inferred solving the well-known mass and momentum balances, which, under the hypothesis of incompressible fluids and neglecting body forces, write:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} &= 0, \\
 \eta \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial z^2} \right) - \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} &= 0, \\
 \eta \left(\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial z^2} \right) - \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} &= 0, \\
 \eta \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial z^2} \right) - \frac{\partial p}{\partial z} &= 0,
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

being u , v , and w the velocity components of each fluid along the x , y , and z directions, η the viscosity, and p the pressure. In the porous subdomain, a modification of the above equations was implemented in order to consider the movement of the fibers as well as the fluid flow through the reinforcement, herein modelled as a moving porous media. The latter term was inferred according to

the well-established Darcy model. Summarizing, each component of the fluid velocity was computed summing two different contributes, as in indicated in Eq. 2:

$$\begin{aligned} u &= U - \frac{K_{xx}}{\eta\phi} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x}, \\ v &= V - \frac{K_{yy}}{\eta\phi} \frac{\partial P}{\partial y}, \\ w &= W - \frac{K_{zz}}{\eta\phi} \frac{\partial P}{\partial z}, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where U , V , and W represent the velocity components of the porous media along the x , y , and z directions, K_{xx} , K_{yy} , K_{zz} are the permeability values along the three axis, and ϕ the reinforcement porosity. Porosity and permeability vary according to geometrical considerations and assuming the Gebart model, preserving always the final fiber volume. In the present investigation a multiphase model was implemented, considering also the presence of the entrapped air.

Figure 3: Impregnation model: computational domain and details from the process

A non-homogeneous approach was adopted, solving different sets of equations for each fluid. In this way, a different velocity field was allowed for each fluid and different effects of the pressure increase on different fluids were also captured. Resin was modelled as a non-isothermal reactive fluid, with temperature and degree of cure dependent viscosity [3]. Heat transfer and resin cure were modeled assuming a non-thermal equilibrium condition and considering each component as a different entity on macro-scale. Therefore a finite temperature difference between solid reinforcement and fluid phases was admitted. As a consequence, besides the continuity and momentum equations for the fluid phase, one energy balance equation for each material was implemented, allowing heat to be transferred between contiguous phases. The temperature field was then inferred obtained solving the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \varphi_f \rho_f C_{p,f} \frac{\partial T_f}{\partial t} + \rho_f C_{p,f} v_{pul} \frac{\partial T_f}{\partial z} = \\
& = \varphi_f \left(k_{x,f} \frac{\partial^2 T_f}{\partial x^2} + k_{y,f} \frac{\partial^2 T_f}{\partial y^2} + k_{z,f} \frac{\partial^2 T_f}{\partial z^2} \right) + Q_{rf} + Q_{af} \\
& \varphi_r \rho_r C_{p,r} \frac{\partial T_r}{\partial t} + \rho_r C_{p,r} \left(u_r \frac{\partial T_r}{\partial x} + v_r \frac{\partial T_r}{\partial y} + w_r \frac{\partial T_r}{\partial z} \right) = \\
& = \varphi_r \left(k_r \frac{\partial^2 T_r}{\partial x^2} + k_r \frac{\partial^2 T_r}{\partial y^2} + k_r \frac{\partial^2 T_r}{\partial z^2} \right) + \varphi_r q + Q_{fr} + Q_{fa} \\
& \varphi_a \rho_a C_{p,a} \frac{\partial T_a}{\partial t} + \rho_a C_{p,a} \left(u_a \frac{\partial T_a}{\partial x} + v_a \frac{\partial T_a}{\partial y} + w_a \frac{\partial T_a}{\partial z} \right) = \\
& = \varphi_a \left(k_a \frac{\partial^2 T_a}{\partial x^2} + k_a \frac{\partial^2 T_a}{\partial y^2} + k_a \frac{\partial^2 T_a}{\partial z^2} \right) + Q_{fa} + Q_{fr}
\end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where the subscripts r, f and a refers to resin, fiber, and air, respectively. In the above equations, φ represents the volume fraction of each material; Q is the interfacial heat transfer between the fluids and the solid phases, depending on the temperature difference, the interfacial area density and the physical properties of the two phases. It is worth noting that in the porous model the DOC was treated as an additional scalar variable with transport properties, existing only in the resin fluid phase only and varying according to a source term constituted by the reaction rate [3-8,11-13,18,19]. Similarly, the heat generation term q , computable as follows:

$$q = \rho_r H_{tr} R_r(\alpha, T), \tag{4}$$

was restricted to the reactive resin and the effect of the exothermic reaction affects the fibers and air temperature by means of conductive heat transfer. In Eq. (4) H_{tr} is the total heat of reaction for the epoxy resin during the exothermic reaction and $R_r(\alpha, T)$ is the cure reaction rate. The dependence of the reaction rate on the absolute temperature and degree of cure was assumed following a semi-empirical autocatalytic model [11]. The software ANSYS-CFX [20] has been used to solve the impregnation model employing a FV numerical scheme.

2.2 Thermo-chemical Analysis.

The thermo-chemical model is based on the coupled solution of the energy equation and a species equation. Taking into account that the void content (air volume fraction) is approximately zero within the die, it is generally assumed that reinforcing fibers are surrounded by only one continuous phase, i.e. the reactive resin. What is more, considering that the velocity components of the fluid resin other than the parallel one to the pulling direction vanish at the beginning of the straight portion of the die, while the parallel component fairly converges to the pulling speed, a further simplification can be obtained assuming a thermal equilibrium condition between resin and fibers. This assumption is supported by the reduced fiber diameter ($\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$) and it was validated in previous investigations [3].

Consequently, the temperature field in the composite material can be inferred solving a unique nonlinear equation, which writes as follows:

$$\rho_c C_{p,c} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + v_{pul} \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right) = k_{x,c} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + k_{y,c} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + k_{z,c} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} + V_r q, \tag{5}$$

particularized using lumped material properties [3-8]. In Eq. (5) T is the temperature, t is the time, ρ_c is the density, $C_{p,c}$ is the specific heat, $k_{x,c}$, $k_{y,c}$ and $k_{z,c}$ are the thermal conductivities of the composite material along x , y and z directions, respectively, and V_r is the resin volume fraction. Finally, the distributions of the degree of cure and reaction rate were obtained assuming the following discretization of the additional variable transport equation:

$$\left(\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} + v_{pul} \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial z} \right) = R_r(\alpha, T). \tag{6}$$

2.3 Stress-strain Analysis.

Some analytical, semi analytical, and numerical models describing stress-strain development in pultrusion have already been discussed in literature [3,8,11-13,18]. Even if, in authors' opinion, aforementioned models cannot be considered as comprehensive and rooms for improvements exist, the effort spent provided a remarkable increase of the knowledge concerning inherent aspects in pultrusion. State-of-the-art models rely on a plane strain hypothesis, considering that the length of the pultruded profiles is much larger than the cross sectional dimensions. The total strain increment is provided by the sum of three different contributions, i.e. elastic, thermal, and chemical. In particular, the elastic one is imputable to internal equilibrium considerations as well as to the action played by the die. The die is usually assumed to be rigid as compared to the part. As a consequence, any expansion of the composite beyond the tool interface is restricted; however the separation due to resin shrinkage is allowed. Taking into account that pultrusion process is relatively fast, viscoelastic effects are commonly neglected, assuming the constitutive model of the material as temperature- and cure-dependent multi-linear elastic (CHILE approach) and homogenizing the material using the self-consistent field micromechanics (SCFM) relationships [8]. More details concerning the derivation of the analytical stress-strain models can be found in [8]. Outcomes provided by the previous models can be used to compute thermal and chemical strain contribution in the stress-strain model.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The simulation of the impregnation step of the pultrusion process of a UD carbon fiber /epoxy composite rod with circular cross section was performed. A scheme of the computational domain has already been provided in Figure 3. The rod radius r was assumed as 4.75 mm, whereas the section ratio (before and after entering the die), was modelled as 1.2. The pulling speed v_{pull} was defined as 5 mm/s. Resin and air volume fraction at the inlet of the computational domain were imposed as the 80% and the 20% of the fiber porosity, whereas the fiber volume fraction in the straight portion of the die was assumed as 0.622. Atmospheric pressure was imposed to fluid phases at the inlet of the domain, assuming a totally uncured resin status at the same boundary. The temperature at the die inlet is assumed to be the resin bath temperature (38°C), while an imposed temperature profile was applied on the die surface, following experimental and numerical data reported in [3,4]. An adiabatic boundary condition was enforced on the last section of the composite workpiece, to consistently close the thermos-chemical problem. Only a quarter of the 3D model was implemented due to symmetry reasons. In the same section, solid and fluid phases were assumed to move at the same velocity, given by the pulling speed.

In Figure 4, some simulation results are shown. As can be seen, the model highlighted the significant pressure rise in the liquid phases when approaching the die inlet. Intriguingly, this increase in pressure was estimated to begin at the center of the work piece before the intersection point. A reasonable explanation motivating this behavior can be found in the reduction of the reinforcement porosity in the tapered inlet until the straight die region is approached. Indeed, a certain amount of resin is prevented from entering the die due to the limited space available between the fibers. As a consequence, the resin in the die tends to slow down the upcoming resin increasing the pressure. What is more, being the excess resin closer to the work piece surface (before entering the die) relatively free to flow away, a more significant pressure increase at the center of the impregnated reinforcement is reasonably expected. In the simulated case, a pressure peak was predicted at the centerline approximately at the beginning of the straight portion of the die, then, the vanishing of the transverse velocity components implied a slight reduction in pressure (with respect to the maximum value). Finally a positive pressure trend was inferred in the simulated straight portion of the die, due to the resin expansion induced by the external heating.

Contour plots in Fig. 4 evidence also the beneficial impact of the pressure increase on the volume fraction of the resin entering the die. Indeed, a direct consequence of the pressure rise was to force the excess of the fluid phases to flow in the opposite direction with respect to the pulling direction, inducing a resin and air backflow. Being the air viscosity lower than the resin viscosity, the effect of the same pressure field was obviously different for the two fluids, as deducible also from Eqs. (1) and (2).

Figure 4: Volume fractions, pressure and velocity fields at die inlet

More specifically, being air was pushed away from the reinforcement, preventing its free inlet into the die and reducing the air volume fraction in the work piece. As can be seen (Fig. 4), streamlines approximately follows pressure contours, until approaching the tapered section of the die, where the maximum air concentration (just before its escaping) was computed. In the same location, escaping bubbles are typically visible in a real pultrusion process. Differently from air, the processing resin was pulled by the moving fibers within the die, whereas its velocity quickly and uniformly converged on the imposed pulling speed.

4 CONCLUSIONS

A computational approach to infer the relevant data to predict the void content in a conventional pultrusion process, based on the integration of an impregnation, a thermo-chemical and a stress-strain model was proposed. The impregnation model was described in details and applied to simulate the processing material at die inlet. Numerical outcomes pointed out the remarkable pressure increase in the tapered zone of the die and its effect on fluid phases. An early pressure increase was predicted before the actual contact between the impregnated reinforcement and the die. The pressure rise at die inlet was found to play a key role pushing air away and reducing the air volume fraction in the straight portion of the die.

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